

CONTRASTING PERSPECTIVES ON INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENT ASSISTANCE IN NORTHEAST NIGERIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ATTITUDES IN PRE-AND-POST INSURGENCY CONTEXTS

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Abstract

Introduction/Background

This study explores shifts in community perceptions of international development assistance in Northeast Nigeria, comparing pre-insurgency (before 2009) attitudes with those in the post-insurgency era (2010 onward). The insurgency by non-state actors (Boko Haram) has immensely impacted the social structures, economy, and trust in external interventions, making it critical to understand how these changes affect local inhabitants' and beneficiaries' attitudes towards international development assistance. While pre-insurgency perspectives seemingly welcomed development assistance for what they are seeing on ground and the general good the IDA has been used for such as fostering infrastructure and economic growth, post-insurgency largely views the IDA with a more cautious approach and with some aura of skepticism, marked by both appreciation for immediate humanitarian relief and criticism regarding dependency and agenda alignment of international donor organizations. This study offers insights to inform more culturally responsive and sustainable aid strategies in conflict-affected areas. The research investigates the shifts in public perception toward international development efforts, aiming to provide insights for policymakers and humanitarian actors.

Methodology

The research employed a mix of survey-based methodology and focused group discussion (FGD) targeting the northeastern states of Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe, areas significantly affected by insurgency and where international aid receipts

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were utilized for various forms of interventions. Using a simple random sampling technique, data were collected from a sample of 384 respondents through structured questionnaires.

Result

The responses were analyzed using simple linear regression to put contrasting Perspectives on International Development Assistance in Northeast Nigeria in context and to determine if there was a shift in attitudes toward international aid in post-insurgency. The results suggest a significant shift in attitudes toward international aid post-insurgency. Pre-insurgency perceptions were predominantly positive, viewing development assistance as a resource base to improve education, healthcare and infrastructure. The work suggests that while aid in pre-insurgency is welcomed for life-saving, the post insurgency perception holds a contrasting opinion of inadequacy in long-term development planning.

Conclusion

Findings suggest that while the pre-insurgency attitudes were generally positive, resilience and skepticism characterize the post-insurgency response, shaped by the immediate needs and long-term distrust stemming from conflict.

Introduction

Northeast Nigeria, particularly the Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe states, also known as the BAY states, has experienced extensive socio-economic disruption due to the ongoing Boko Haram insurgency. This study examines changing perspectives on international development assistance from two-time frames: pre-insurgency (before 2009) and post-insurgency (2010 onward). The influx of aid post-2010 has often been life-saving; some government ministries and community members' attitudes vary based on their direct or indirect experiences with international assistance in periods of insurgency. Understanding these perspectives is essential

for improving engagement and effectiveness in development efforts.

Northeast Nigeria has been significantly affected by the ongoing insurgency led by Boko Haram, particularly impacting the Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe states. Before 2009, this region was relatively stable, and attitudes toward international development assistance were generally positive. Communities saw development aid as a means to enhance local infrastructure, health services, education, and livelihoods. However, the onset of violent insurgency introduced an extended period of instability and humanitarian crises, fundamentally altering the local socio-political landscape and reshaping community needs and priorities.

In the post-insurgency context, international development agencies shifted their focus toward immediate relief and recovery, including food distribution, healthcare, and resettlement assistance. This shift in focus was met with a complex blend of gratitude for humanitarian aid and emerging concerns around dependency, transparency, and long-term planning. At some point, state governments in the BAY states placed an embargo on donor agencies' support and the activities of NGOs operating in their states. Understanding these changing perceptions becomes essential to designing effective, sustainable aid programs that align with aspirations and local needs, support trust building, and foster resilience. This comparative study investigates these attitudinal changes, offering a nuanced understanding of the impact of international aid over time in conflict and post-conflict settings.

Literature Review

International development assistance, just as seen in other climes, has also played a critical role in the economic development of Nigeria in general. This assistance program played a very crucial role in addressing the socio-economic challenges facing the Northeast region and Nigeria as a whole, particularly in response to the insurgency triggered by Boko Haram. This literature review examines the contrasting perspectives on development aid in Northeast Nigeria, comparing attitudes in pre-insurgency and post-insurgency contexts, with a focus on

both the government, community, and citizens' perceptions on one hand, and its impact on local resilience, and challenges related to dependency and sustainability.

International Development Assistance in Pre-Insurgency Contexts

Before the insurgency escalated in 2009, Northeast Nigeria experienced relatively stable conditions where development assistance was developmental and primarily targeted economic growth, infrastructure, health services, and education improvement (Zenn & Pearson, 2014). Communities in the pre-insurgency period generally held positive attitudes towards international aid, viewing it as a necessary and welcome intervention that supported infrastructure development and improved access to essential services (Ojo & Udofia, 2018). Citizens and the government looked up to aid which came in the form of food, shelter, water, sanitation, hygiene, educational support, and health services including infrastructure development like urban roads and markets as immediate support for getting out of harm's way. Development agencies such as the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and World Bank, the United Nations Food Program provided food, materials, funding, and expertise aimed at addressing poverty and improving livelihoods, which reinforced the region's acceptance of foreign aid (Chukwuemeka et al., 2019). This assistance contributed to economic stability, recovery, and development, with

community members seeing foreign aid as a beneficial partnership that supported local growth without substantial disruption to social structures (Mustapha, 2016). The pre-insurgency perception by citizens and government is built on “saviour” mentality – that is, a situation where the citizens find solace in donors, without feeling there is any string attached.

Shifting Attitudes in the Post-Insurgency Context

The onset of insurgency was a total coarse; it brought widespread violence, displacement, and humanitarian crises, drastically altering the social landscape and the role of development assistance in the region (Onuoha, 2014). In response to the conflict, international organizations shifted their focus from development-oriented aid to humanitarian relief, prioritizing immediate needs such as Education in emergencies, food security, healthcare, and shelter for internally displaced persons (IDPs) (Awojobi, 2014). This shift was met with a mixed response from local communities, who expressed appreciation for life-saving interventions while also developing concerns regarding the long-term effects of aid dependency and the limited focus on sustainable development (Campbell & Harwood, 2018).

In the post-insurgency context, there is evidence of a growing ambivalence toward international development assistance. While the aid provided

during the insurgency period addressed critical needs, some sections of the government, community members, and citizens began to question the motives of foreign organizations and expressed frustration over perceived inequalities in aid distribution (Agbibo, 2020). Critics argue that international aid interventions in conflict zones often fail to address the root causes of instability, leading to temporary relief rather than sustainable improvements in local resilience (Sanda & Hassan, 2022). Additionally, the prolonged reliance on external assistance has contributed to an environment where communities may experience reduced agency and a sense of dependency on aid (Barnett & Weiss, 2011). Impliedly, productivity is reduced, and the aid becomes counterproductive in terms of the overall economic development of the northeast region and the country as a whole. This assertion lends credence to a development where ammunition and other illegal items are found with development agencies. There is a growing suspicion of the aid agencies that had been the only ones able to broker a truce and got some of the abducted Chibok girls released by the non-state actors

Impact on Community Resilience and Local Trust

The insurgency and subsequent influx of aid brought about the issue of trust and charity to the front burner and a subject of local discourse. Scholars have noted that post-insurgency

communities in Northeast Nigeria increasingly regard aid programs cautiously, as their experiences have revealed potential disparities between foreign aid objectives and community priorities (Agbiboa, 2020; Attfield, 2019). For instance, during a focused group discussion, some community leaders argue that while international organizations promote a culture of resilience, their programs often fail to incorporate local voices and adapt to the complexities of cultural and social norms within affected regions (Onuoha, 2014). They also argued that some of the aid programs are completely in contradiction with the belief system of the beneficiaries and citizens of recipient countries, this is evident in the pressing for gender conformity in many of the request for proposals and the proposals submitted by local NGOs for funding.

Post-insurgency attitudes also reflect concerns over the unintended consequences of aid, particularly regarding local economic disruption and the erosion of traditional structures that once supported community cohesion (Chukwuemeka et al., 2019). Studies show that although humanitarian aid has brought significant short-term benefits, the conspicuous absence of long-term development planning may contribute to an unsustainable reliance on international aid (Awojobi, 2014). In regions like the Northeast Nigeria where the Boko haram insurgency weakened local resilience mechanisms, the effectiveness of development

aid is contingent upon international actors' willingness to partner closely with local organizations and prioritize capacity-building initiatives (Mustapha, 2016). However, this might be far from it because of international politics and the silent aid policies. Based on growing concerns by the Nigerian government with regards to international aid and local content, a deliberate move by agencies in this direction is noticed. This underscores the current willingness of aid agencies to buy into the localization policy which arrogates certain responsibilities and partnership priorities to local NGOs by the International NGOs.

Challenges of Dependency and Aid Effectiveness

The literature highlights the critical issue of dependency by government and communities and the complexities involved in managing aid generally and in conflict-prone areas in particular. Development practitioners and researchers argue that international assistance, while so important in this context, can risk creating a cycle of dependency that diminishes community productivity (Barnett & Weiss, 2011). In Northeast Nigeria, communities that once viewed aid as a means to empower local development now increasingly perceive aid as a temporary relief measure that may inadvertently inhibit self-reliance and sustainable growth (Campbell & Harwood, 2018). Additionally, scholars emphasize the need for foreign aid organizations to evaluate

their strategies to minimize dependency syndrome on the part of beneficiaries and create pathways that reinforce local capacity and self-sufficiency (Sanda & Hassan, 2022). One school of thought has it that insurgency persisted because it has become an easy virtue to make a fortune without hard work. It is said that man naturally detests labour and hardwork, thus proving proponents of this thought right.

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to explore attitudes toward international development assistance in Northeast Nigeria, contrasting pre-and-post-insurgency perceptions. By combining quantitative and qualitative methods, the research seeks to capture both statistical data and rich, narrative insights. This methodology allows a nuanced understanding of how prolonged conflict affects local communities' views on aid. Additionally, it considers how various factors, such as social context and exposure to insurgency-related violence, shape perceptions (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

Study Design

The study design is cross-sectional, collecting data on current attitudes through surveys and in-depth interviews. Pre-insurgency data are retrospectively gathered from secondary sources, including archived survey data, reports, and oral histories with community elders and leaders of thought who can speak to the changes observed over time. This study design facilitates

a comparative analysis that shows the views and perceptions of beneficiary attitudes in times of stability and those that stem from conflict (Yin, 2018).

Study Setting

Data was gathered from three key states affected by the insurgency: Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe. These areas were selected due to the high level of impact and activity created by the insurgency. These states represent Northeast Nigeria's hardest-hit areas, with significant humanitarian and development needs exacerbated by conflict. Within each state, data are collected from both urban and rural areas that are accessible to capture a diversity of experiences and perceptions regarding international aid, it provided valuable insights into how violent conflict can alter perceptions of international aid.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Participants included individuals aged 18 and older who resided in the selected states for at least five years before and after 2009. Those who could not recall pre-insurgency conditions or had lived outside these areas were excluded to ensure focused insights.

Population sampling

The target population includes adults aged 18 and above who have resided in these states for at least five years pre-insurgency and during the insurgency period. This timeframe ensures participants have sufficient exposure to the region's socio-political changes.

Sample Size Determination

A sample size of 400 participants was calculated using a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, determined through Cochran's sample size formula for a finite population (Cochran, 1977). Given the study's focus on multiple regions and community segments, stratified sampling was employed to ensure representative sampling across states and rural-urban divides.

Sampling Procedures

Participants were selected through a combination of stratified and snowball sampling. Initial participants from community leaders, local NGOs, and representatives of local organizations helped identify others within their networks. This approach was particularly effective in rural or conflict-sensitive areas where trust is crucial, allowing the researcher to access individuals who might otherwise be reluctant to participate (Patton, 2014).

Data Collection and Preparation

Quantitative data were gathered through structured questionnaires, while qualitative data were collected via in-depth interviews. Data preparation included transcription of interviews, translation (where necessary), and anonymization to maintain participant confidentiality.

Quantitative Data Collection

Quantitative data were collected through structured questionnaires. Questions focused on participants' perceptions of development aid effectiveness, their trust in international organizations, and their views on aid dependency. A Likert scale was used for participants to rate their level of agreement with various statements regarding international aid (e.g., "I believe international aid has improved local infrastructure" or "International aid increases dependency"). The questionnaire was pre-tested to assess reliability and validity, ensuring clarity and cultural appropriateness in its phrasing (Bryman, 2016).

Qualitative Data Collection

Qualitative data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with selected participants from the survey sample, particularly community leaders, aid workers, and local NGOs. Interviews explored nuanced perceptions of international aid, allowing participants to reflect on personal experiences and community attitudes over time. This approach enables in-depth insights into the complex factors shaping perceptions of aid in conflict-prone areas (Ritchie et al., 2013).

Data Preparation

Quantitative data were anonymized, coded, and input into statistical software (SPSS) for analysis. For qualitative data, interviews were recorded with participant consent, transcribed, and translated where necessary. Transcriptions were coded thematically to identify patterns and

emerging themes relevant to the research question.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including chi-square tests to identify significant differences in attitudes between pre- and post-insurgency periods. Qualitative data were coded thematically to identify recurring patterns in participants' narratives.

Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative data were analyzed by means of descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize attitudes toward international aid in each period. Inferential analyses, including chi-square tests, were conducted to determine if there were statistically significant differences in attitudes across demographic groups and between pre- and post-insurgency contexts.

Qualitative Analysis

Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, identifying key themes related to trust, aid dependency, perceived effectiveness, and sustainability of aid interventions. NVivo

software was used to assist with coding and pattern recognition, allowing the researcher to explore the intersections between quantitative findings and qualitative narratives (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Results and Discussions

Results indicate a notable shift in attitudes toward international aid post-insurgency. Pre-insurgency perceptions were predominantly positive, viewing development assistance as a means to improve infrastructure, healthcare, and education.

Source: Research survey 2024

However, post-insurgency attitudes reflect mixed feelings: while there is an appreciation for life-saving humanitarian aid, there is also a perception of something for something (Quid pro quo donation) showing the intent of donor to benefit from certain favour or services in exchange for their gift, they perceive that donations come with strings attached (conditional donations), strategic philanthropy / corporate sponsorship meant to shove up their reputation, access markets, or receive tax or branding benefits in case of companies, they also perceive inadequacies in long-term development planning.

How would you rate the effectiveness of international development assistance in addressing immediate humanitarian needs (e.g., food, shelter, medical care)?

411 responses

Source: Research survey 2024

Additionally, some participants expressed concerns about dependency on aid and felt that international organizations often prioritize their own agenda as opposed to the wishes of the beneficiaries. Beyond this palpable economic dependency, they agreed that donor dependency comes with numerous forms of biases/distortions that have a severe impact on the communities and governance systems.

Many of the respondents expressed different biases in line with donor aid in humanitarian settings, like bias in beneficiary targeting and selection, which excludes communities and individuals from selection because of donor priorities, not necessarily the greatest needs. Many other donors set priorities based on a skewed true picture of vulnerability, poverty, or resilience as exaggerated in proposals.

Participants' concern also stems from policy bias or donor-driven agenda, a situation where a country's spending plan can shift based on

To what extent has international development assistance increased your dependency for funds on International community?

407 responses

donor funding streams instead of local development priorities and plans.

Conclusion

This study reveals a shift from general acceptance of international aid pre-insurgency to a nuanced mix of reliance and skepticism in post-insurgency. The post-insurgency attitudes highlight the need for global organizations to engage with local communities to ensure aid initiatives' suitability, including sustainability and cultural alignment. The profoundness of international development assistance to communities with all its intent and purpose, should be accompanied by the same degree of openness to ensure transparency and accountability.

The study further revealed that the International Development Assistance program provided much-needed lifelines in contexts of fragility, conflict, and displacement especially in Northeast Nigeria, where many years of violence

and instability prevailed. Further research is warranted to closely examine interventions in humanitarian relief, livelihoods recovery, health, education, and governance on a wider scale, and how they have helped to stabilize lives, restore hope, and foster pathways to resilience in conflict-affected areas, such as Northeast Nigeria. Having agreed on the inherent tension between short-term relief and long-term development, including the risks of dependency, policy distortion, and unequal access that external aid can introduce, further studies can still reveal its nuances in relation to long-term development.

Ultimately, the study upheld the notion that international assistance must go beyond delivering aid; donor assistance should strengthen local institutions, build community capacity, and empower stakeholders like women, youth, and marginalized groups believed to be key actors in recovery and development. However, sustainable impact means moving away from external driven priorities to locally owned or improvised solutions capable of addressing structural inequalities and social cohesion in the affected areas.

Ethical Considerations

The study received ethical approval from the appropriate local and academic review boards. Participant confidentiality was strictly maintained, with anonymized responses and secure data storage practices. Written informed

consent was obtained from each participant, who was briefed on the study's objectives, procedures, and their rights, including the option to withdraw at any time without consequence (World Medical Association, 2013).

Study Limitations

Limitations include potential recall bias among older participants and challenges in accessing remote areas affected by insurgency. The exclusion of certain regions due to security issues may limit the generalizability of findings across the broader Northeast region.

Declaration

The authors declare no conflict of interest in conducting this study. Ethical approval was obtained from relevant local authorities and participants provided informed consent.

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